

Alkali Metals and Structure of $[MX_6]^{4-}$ Ions : Octahedral Structure of A_2MX_4 and AMX_3 Type Complexes

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The complexes of the types A_2MX_4 and AMX_3 (where A = alkali metals; M = Be, Mg and 3d-transition metals; X = F and Cl) have tetragonal and distorted octahedral structures respectively. Varied distortion from regular octahedral geometry is due to the covalent bonding between A-X. The species $[MX_6]^{4-}$ acts as ligand where the donating sites are halogen atoms and forms complexes with alkali metals. The structures have been substantiated by ir spectra and crystals structure data.

Novelty of the alkali metal complexes containing 'metal complexes as ligands' has been attracting the chemists for the last three decades. Physiological application encouraged the chemists to go ahead with their work to find out carriers for their transportation in biological kingdom. Work has been extended with 'metal complexes as ligands' in which the donating sites are halogen atoms.

Discussion

A_2MX_4 and AMX_3 type complexes are actually polymers. From crystallographic studies, it has been observed that complexes of the type A_2MX_4 (where A = alkali metals; M = Mg and 3d-transition metals; X = F and Cl) are iso-structural and resemble the structure of K_2NiF_4 which is tetragonal¹, and each Ni^{2+} is octahedrally surrounded by F^- ions. The octahedra share four F^- ions in a plane containing a layer of Ni^{2+} and two F^- ions above and below the plane are not shared. The compounds of the formula AMX_3 (where A = alkali metals; M = Be, Mg and 3d-transition metals; X = F and Cl) contain $[MX_6]^{4-}$ ions as structural units. In the case of $CsNiCl_3$, coordination about Ni is perfect

octahedral, whereas in other cases it is distorted, but the extent of distortion varies which is maximum in the cases of $Cr^{2,3}$ and Cu^{2-4} .

Factors responsible for the distortion from normal octahedral geometry may be due to (i) variation of d^n system or (ii) presence of alkali metals. As there has been no definite regularity in the distortion so J.T. distortion can not be the only fundamental factor for the distortion. However, presence of alkali metals may be responsible factor for the distortion.

In the case of complexes of the type AMX_3 and A_2MX_4 , X atoms are bridged as M—X—M.

Bridging $\nu_b(M-Cl)$ stretching frequencies²⁸ usually occur below 200 cm^{-1} : $Co(Py)_2Cl_2$, 186 cm^{-1} ; $Co[4-Cl(Py)]_2Cl_2$, 185 cm^{-1} ; $Co[4-Br(Py)]_2Cl_2$, 185 cm^{-1} .

From Table 1, it is clear that there has been considerable lowering in the M-Cl stretching frequencies in $AMCl_3$ and A_2MCl_4 complexes.

As the coordination number of central metal ion never goes up, it points out that there may be bridging of the type,

TABLE I

Compd.	X—M̂—X angle (°)	ν _{M-X} cm ⁻¹	Sum ^a of the ionic radii of A and X atoms (Å)	Sum ^a of the van der Waals radii of A and X atoms (Å)	Observed A—X distance by X-ray (Å)			
K ₂ MgCl ₄ ^b	—	176	3.19	4.70	3.503,	3.331,	3.071 ^b	
K ₂ MgF ₄ ^c	—	—	2.74	4.40	2.64 ^c			
Cs ₂ CrCl ₄ ^d	—	170	3.50	4.25	3.46,	3.42,	3.41 ^{d,e}	
Rb ₂ MnCl ₄ ^f	—	170	3.18	4.06	3.44,	3.24 ^f		
Cs ₂ MnCl ₄ ^g	—	172	3.50	4.25	3.65,	3.48 ^g		
Rb ₂ MnF ₄ ^h	—	—	2.85	3.76	2.87,	2.84,	2.82 ^h	
Rb ₂ FeF ₄ ^h	—	—	2.85	3.76	2.86,	2.84,	2.83 ^h	
K ₂ CoF ₄ ⁱ	—	—	2.74	4.40	2.67,	2.66,	2.64 ^k	
K ₂ NiF ₄ ^{h,j}	—	—	2.74	4.40	2.63 ^c			
K ₂ CuF ₄ ^{c,k}	—	—	2.74	4.40	2.94,	2.77,	2.59 ^c	
K ₂ ZnF ₄ ^l	—	—	2.74	4.40	2.66,	2.65,	2.64 ^l	
CsBeF ₃ ^m	109 ^m	—	3.05	3.95	3.47,	3.17,	2.99,	2.96 ^m
CsMgCl ₃ ⁿ	103.4 ⁿ	174 ^w	3.50	4.25	3.81,	3.63 ⁿ		
CsCrCl ₃ ^o	—	163 ^w	3.50	4.25	3.63,	3.47,	3.43,	3.42 ^e
CsMnCl ₃ ^p	85.3 ^q	158 ^w	3.50	4.25	3.77,	3.64 ^p		
NaMnCl ₃ ^r	83.3 ^r	—	2.83	4.20	2.90,	2.71 ^r		
CsFeF ₃ ^s	—	—	3.05	3.95	3.21,	3.15,	3.12,	3.05 ^s
CsCoCl ₃ ^t	—	165 ^w	3.50	4.25	3.75,	3.60 ^t		
CsNiCl ₃ ^{u,v}	—	179 ^w	3.50	4.25	3.86,	3.48,	3.47,	3.46 ^u
CsCuCl ₃ ^x	—	158 ^w	3.50	4.25	3.82,	3.69,	3.56,	3.40 ^x

^aRefs. 25, 26. ^bRef. 5. ^cRef. 6. ^dRef. 7. ^eRef. 8. ^fRef. 9. ^gRef. 10. ^hRef. 11. ⁱRef. 12. ^jRef. 1. ^kRef. 13. ^lRef. 14. ^mRef. 15. ⁿRef. 16. ^oRef. 17. ^pRef. 18. ^qRef. 19. ^rRef. 20. ^sRef. 21. ^tRef. 22. ^uRef. 23. ^vRef. 24. ^wRef. 27. ^xRef. 4.

i.e. at some places covalency of chlorine atom would be three. Again it is quite clear that distance between A—X in AMX₃ and A₂MX₄ type complexes, is less than the sum of van der Waals atomic radii of respective atoms, and in some cases even less than the sum of the ionic radii. Thus it can be suggested that A and X atoms are at a very close distance, i.e. there is some sort of covalent bonding between the two.

Stability trend of the complexes do not follow Irving-William's rule²⁹. Since A is coordinated to X so (MX₆) groups acts as a ligand. Due to the covalent bonding between A—X, the (MX₆) octahedra are pressurised. It is the degree of covalent bonding between A—X bonds, which determines the extent of distortion.

Structures of the complexes of both types have been suggested in Figs. 1 and 2.

Fig. 1 Structure of AMX₃ type complexes (Fig. 1) is polymeric and (MX₆) octahedra share its all faces with other octahedra.

Fig. 2 Structure of A_2MX_4 type complexes (Fig. 2) is polymeric and (MX_6) octahedra share its four faces only with other octahedra.

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